

Fig S15. Protrusion component f_{prot} extracted from the experimental cell track of Fig 7 for varying relative weights $r_{\text{prot}} \in \{0.05, 0.5, 0.8\}$ (vertical axis) and $r_{\text{APCSF}} \in \{0.01, 0.05, 0.1\}$ (horizontal axis) as well as varying overall velocity parameter $w_f \in \{1, 5, 10, 20\}$ (page axis). The correlation coefficient ρ between the protrusion component and the fluorescence intensity kymograph from Fig 7D is displayed above each kymograph. Regions of interest are displayed as black and white dashed boxes.

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